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<https://www.nextfood-project.eu/>

Nextfood - Educating the next generation of professionals in the agrifood system

Practice Abstract #11: Towards a profitable and sustainable forestry chain - Increased quality and number of micro-habitats for enhanced biodiversity

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There is an increasing interest in balancing economic and environmental aspects during roundwood harvesting from areas with high natural values. There is also an unproven agreement among researchers, forestry personnel and machine operators that a skilled operator often can improve or even create habitats for flora and fauna during certain conditions in an efficient way to a modest extra cost. Skogforsk is running a case aiming at a higher understanding about logging techniques, strategies and methods to increase quality and number of micro-habitats in production forests. Our case is conducted as a vocational course for forestry professionals. We will use the Nextfood model to develop and implement the course. Figure 1. The Nextfood model for teaching and learning in agrifood and forestry education. The iterative process of planning, implementing and reflecting. After the first meeting conducted at an ongoing logging operation, all participants agreed that the model could be very fruitful to allow researchers, management and operators to learn from each other. As a first step each participant, forestry professionals as well as researchers were asked to write down what they most of all would like to teach the other participants and what they most of all would like to learn. Their answers create a platform for the upcoming case. A planning workshop with the team of researchers was held at Skogforsk in Uppsala in September 2019. During the workshop an activity plan for the first cycle of the Nextfood model was created.